

EVALUATION OF ANTIBACTERIAL, ANTIFUNGAL, AND ANTIOXIDANT POTENTIAL OF Cr-DOPED MANGANESE OXIDE NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract

Nanoparticles are being used for the treatment of many diseases due to their antifungal, antiviral, antibacterial and antioxidant activity. Present research was carried out to analyze the antibacterial, antioxidant and antifungal potential of Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticles. For the synthesis of nanoparticles sol-gel method was used because it is easy and inexpensive. *Klebsiella pneumonia* was used against seven antibiotics. Antibacterial activity of nanoparticles with different concentrations (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1) was tested against *E.coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* and Ciprofloxacin was applied as positive control. In *Bacillus subtilis*, the largest zone of inhibition was seen at doses of 0.1, and there was no zone of inhibition at 0.025 and 0.05. The zone of inhibition was present in *E. coli* at doses of 0.025, 0.075, and 0.1, with a maximum at 0.05. Ciprofloxacin showed the maximum zone of inhibition against both *Bacillus subtilis* and *E.coli* as compared to nanoparticles. Antifungal potential of the prepared nanoparticles was assessed against *Fusarium equesiti* and *Rhizopus stolonifer*. The activity was assessed on 3rd, 5th and 7th day. The development of *Rhizopus stolonifer* was not affected by the antifungal properties of Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticles. It began to expand on the third day and continued to grow the same on days five and seven. The findings of the antioxidant activity test shows that ascorbic acid and Cr oxide NPs both exhibit antioxidant activity. Ascorbic acid has 83% antioxidant activity at the same concentration as Cr oxide NPs, which has maximal antioxidant activity of 99%. The minimum antioxidant activity of the test sample is 89% at 0.1 concentrations. The results of antibacterial, antifungal and antioxidant activity proved that the Cr doped manganese oxide can be used

as antibacterial, antifungal and antioxidant drug.

INTRODUCTION:

One of the most interesting areas of nanotechnology is the use of nanoparticles (NP) in medicine (Schrand et al., 2010). NPs are being employed in gene therapy (Raffi et al., 2008), medication delivery (Vijayalakshmi & Sivaraj, 2015), and the detection (Zharov et al., 2005) and cure of tumor (Chen et al., 2005). The scientific and medical communities are particularly interested in these uses of metal oxide NP in biomedicine (Wong et al., 2009) and cancer treatment (Rasmussen et al., 2010). Copper oxide NPs (CuO NP) has anticancer characteristics, likely by eliminating tumor cells through direct contact or the induction of oxidative stress (Siddiqui et al., 2013). CuO NPs are a promising possibility for cancer therapy because it has been found that they preferentially destroy tumor cells in a dose-dependent method without harming regular cells (Gurr et al., 2005). A novel class of alternative anticancer drugs, complexes comprising copper or other metals, has emerged (Alaraby et al., 2017).

Copper nanoparticles (Cu NPs) have drawn a lot of interest as possible candidates for cutting-edge antimicrobial (i.e., antifouling, antifungal, antibacterial, and antiviral) (Dheeb et al., 2019) usage as antibiotic, biocides treatment alternatives, and nanocomposite coatings (Cioffi et al., 2005). An extensive bandgap (3.4 eV), a high melting temperature, and enhanced constancy are just a few of the distinctive physicochemical characteristics of the nanoparticle Cr_2O_3 that make it stand out among other metal oxides-based nanoparticles (Iqbal et al., 2020). In many various applications, such as catalysis, photonics, coating materials, improved colorants, etc., Cr_2O_3 nanoparticles have been widely used. When compared to other chromium oxides, trivalent Cr_2O_3 nanoparticles are thought to be the most stable (Ahmed Mohamed et al., 2020). Despite being a promising material, only a lesser number of studies have inspected Cr_2O_3 nanoparticles for various biological applications

because to the possibility of their harmful effects, which have been noted in numerous investigations. For Cr_2O_3 nanoparticles to be used in various biological systems, biocompatibility is a crucial factor. By covering or functionalizing the surfaces of Cr_2O_3 nanoparticles with biogenic molecules, the toxins they produce can be lessened. The surface coating of Cr_2O_3 with biogenic phytochemicals from plants is one of the most promising methods for accomplishing this (Khan et al., 2021).

Current study was carried out antifungal activity of $\text{Mn}_{0.80}\text{Cr}_{0.18}\text{O}_2$ nanoparticle against fungi (*Rhizopus stolonifer* and *Fusarium equesiti*), susceptibility and resistance of different antibiotics against bacteria (*Klebsiella pneumonia*), the antibacterial activity of nanoparticle $\text{Mn}_{0.80}\text{Cr}_{0.18}\text{O}_2$ against *E.coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* and the antioxidant activity of $\text{Mn}_{0.80}\text{Cr}_{0.18}\text{O}_2$ nanoparticle.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in this experiment were obtained from the different labs of The University of Punjab. Sample was made by mixing 1.896 g of KMnO_4 and 0.29 g of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in 100 mL of water, adding 1% SDS solution to the mixture, shifting it to an autoclave, and then adding 20 mL of HCl to the reaction mixture. After stirring the mixture for 30 minutes, the autoclave was shut and heated for 24 hours at 180 °C. After heating, the autoclave was opened and allowed to cool to room temperature. Dark powder was produced at the base of the autoclave. The extremely fine powdered substance was filtered and then washed with sufficient distilled water. The substance, which was obtained as a dark powder, was assessed for catalytic activity.

PXRD; 2θ (12.5, 17.4, 26.4, 34.5, 41.2, 53.6, 62.4, 72.4) D (40.89±4); FTIR cm^{-1} 536 v (Mn-O) (1340, 1634). Elemental percentage composition (by EDX) found for $\text{Mn}_{0.80}\text{Cr}_{0.18}\text{O}_2$ is Mn 42.10; Cr 6.94; O 50.76.

Brunauer-Emmett-teller (BET), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis are used to characterize these materials and gain complete understanding of their properties and structures.

Antibacterial activity

University supplied the *Klebsiella pneumonia* used in the in vitro antibacterial investigation. In accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, the culture was revived. For 24 hours, *Klebsiella pneumonia* was allowed to develop in a 37 °C incubator before being transferred to a 4 °C refrigerator until required.

Antimicrobial susceptibility test

Disc diffusion method

Following this technique, the disc diffusion method was used to test seven antibiotics (Levofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Trimethoprim, Amoxicillin, and Ciprofloxacin). Five distinct concentrations of nanoparticles (20 mg, 40 mg, 60 mg, 80 mg, and 100 mg) were collected using the disk diffusion method. The antibiotic levofloxacin served as the standard.

Agar-well diffusion method

The antibacterial activity of the nanoparticle against the strains of bacteria of *Bacillus subtilis* and *E. coli* was examined using the agar-well diffusion technique. The bacterial isolates were initially cultured for 18 hours in nutritional broth to standardize them to 0.5 McFarland values (106 cfu mL⁻¹) before use. The McFarland standard of 0.5 was made by mixing 0.5 mL of 0.048 M BaCl₂ with 99.5 mL of 0.36 N H₂SO₄. A test tube with a screw-on top was filled with the prescribed amount of the barium sulfate turbidity standard (4-6 mL).

Nutrient agar (MERCK) was dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water with a pH of 7.0 to create the nutrient agar medium, which was then autoclaved. It was permitted to cool to 45 °C. The 75 mL of seeded nutritional agar was poured into petri dishes and let to harden. A sterile cork borer with a 6 mm diameter was used to drill

wells into the agar. The wells were filled with 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1mg/ml of Cr doped manganese oxide, which was then left to stand at room temperature for roughly 2 hours before being incubated at 37 °C. Parallel controls were established for the usage of the different solvents to fill the wells. After 24 hours, the plates were checked for areas of inhibition. The results were contrasted with Ciprofloxacin at a 5 microgram concentration.

Antifungal activity

The manufactured NPs' antifungal activity was tested using the agar well diffusion method. Fungal cultures grown on potato dextrose medium were utilized to investigate the antifungal potency of selected NPs.

Antibiotics, 500ml of distilled water, 10g of agar, 125g of potato starch, and 10g of glucose were combined to create potato dextrose agar. To prevent any bacterial growth, streptomycin was also added. The potato dextrose agar was autoclaved for 15 minutes at 121°C and 15 pounds of pressure. Potato dextrose agar was poured onto plates, then left to set. A 5mm conventional cork borer was used to drill wells into the agar plate after the culture plates had had time to harden in the laminar airflow chamber. *Fusarium* and *Rhizopus* fungus cultures were isolated from papaya and persimmon. Different amounts of NPs (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1 mg/ml) were applied to the appropriate wells. The control method utilized was fungicide. After that, the plates were sealed and incubated for 3 days at 252 °C. Results were seen at 3, 5, and 7 days later.

Antioxidant activity

Preparation of DPPH

In a measuring flask, 9.85 mg of DPPH was added before being dissolved with methanol. After the DPPH had completely dissolved in the methanol and there were no more solid particles, 50ml of methanol was added, and the mixture was vigorously shaken. The resulting solution was kept at room temperature in a dark cabinet for 30 minutes.

2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) method

The process was carried out in line via Bhakya et al. (2016) with a little alteration. The capacity of ascorbic acid and Cr doped manganese oxide nanostructures to scavenge free radicals was evaluated using the stable radical DPPH. A freshly produced DPPH solution (1 mM in methanol) was added to 1 ml of different Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticle concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75, and 100 mg/ml) and forcefully vortexed. Various concentrations of these particles (0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, 0.1, 0.15, and 0.2mg/2ml) were created as solutions in distilled water. The combination was then let to rest for 30 minutes at ambient temperature in the dark. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Systronics, AU-2701). The control contained all the reagents except the sample: 1.5 ml of distilled water, 1.5 ml of methanol, and 1 ml of DPPH. The percentage of inhibition was used to compute the efficiency of the free radical scavenging process using the formula below.

$$\% \text{ of scavenging} = \frac{P_c - P_s}{P_c} \times 100$$

Where P_c is the absorbance of control and P_s is the absorption of CrNPs/ascorbic acid.

RESULTS

Characterization

PXRD Results

Results from the PXRD of Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticle indicated the presence of

MnO_2 as the predominant phase and the minor inclusion of CrO_3 and $MnCrO_4$. The acquired patterns demonstrated that the peak for MnO_2 had consistently decreased in strength from sample as the incorporation of Cr increased under the influence of the peaks for CrO_3 . Tetragonal in shape and belonging to the $P4_2/mnm$ space group, MnO_2 's primary phase. The PXRD results further support the samples' monocrystalline nature and table-listed elemental makeup.

The computed average crystallite size for sample was found to be 40.89. It has been taken into consideration that the chromium incorporation increased crystallite size and consequently led to the crystal stress depicted in Table 1. According to the dislocation density values, nanomaterial exhibits lower levels of defect, smaller crystallite sizes, and consequently improved stability. The value of the crystalline volume shows that the samples' regular O lattice sites have been properly incorporated with chromium ions. Chromium ions cause an increase in crystal strain and crystal imperfection when they are present in the structure of MnO_2 . The lattice contraction that was identified during the calculation of the lattice parameters may be the cause of the nanomaterial's positive tensile micro strain values.

Figure 1: PXRD spectra of NPs

Table 1: PXRD parameters of nanocatalyst

Sample	Cr doped manganese oxide
Found Composition	$Mn_{0.80}Cr_{0.18}O_2$
Average Crystallite Size D (nm)	40.89 ± 4
Volume $V=D^3$	66629
Dislocation Density $\times 10^{-3} (nm)^{-2} (\delta)$	3.36×10^4
Micro Strain (ϵ)	0.027

SEM Results:

Figure 2 displays a SEM image of the nanomaterial, and Table 2 lists its surface

morphological characteristics. The amorphous form of the nanocatalyst was shown by a SEM scan.

Table 2: Morphological properties of the prepared nanocatalyst by SEM Image

Sample	Cr doped manganese oxide
Material Nature	Amorphous
Dispersity	Heterodisperse
Structural Appearance	Rod - like Structure

Figure 2: SEM image of NPs

BET Results

According to Table 3, the specific surface area of nanomaterials was calculated using the multipoint BET methodology and the pore structure of the nanomaterials was estimated

using the DFT method. It was observed that the constant C value for the sample was less than 100, indicating a strong adsorbate-adsorbent interaction.

Table 3: BET Characteristics of Prepared Nanocatalyst

Sample	Cr doped manganese oxide
Surface Area (S_{BET}) (m^2/g)	38.86
Pore Volume (V_m) (cc/g)	0.016
Pore Width (nm)	3.40
Constant	98.654

FTIR Results

All of the distinctive signals of the samples were visible in the Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of sample as depicted in Figure. Peaks below 750 cm^{-1} confirm the vibration of the Mn-O bond, while the Mn-O str. bond is 521.22 cm^{-1} . High structural Symmetry is revealed by a simple FTIR pattern.

Figure 3: FTIR Spectra of NPs

Photo-luminescence (PL)

Studies on photo-luminescence (PL) are conducted by using a 375 nm excitation wavelength and recording the sample's spectra.

Sample displayed an emission peak with increasing strength at 410 nm. The spectra obtained in the larger range of 400 to 470 nm demonstrate that the synthesized material can be

an excellent source to absorb UV light and emit visible light, making it a good charge carrier or migrant material and having the potential to be employed as a photo-catalyst. Figure's

representation of the sample's PL spectra reveals that sample had the lowest PL emission intensity at a 430 nm excitation wavelength.

Figure 4: PL spectra of NPs

Antibacterial assay

The growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* was tested against seven different antibiotics (Levofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Trimethoprim, Amoxicillin and Ciprofloxacin). The table below displays the impact of

nanoparticles on seven different antibiotics. Levofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin inhibited the growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* but there was no effect of Trimethoprim, Amoxicillin on the growth of bacteria

Figure 5: Effect of antibiotics on the growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia*

Table 4 Table shows the antibacterial property of antibiotics against *Klebsiella pneumonia*

Antibiotics	Symbols	Concentration	Susceptible	Intermediately susceptible	Resistant	Findings	Results
1.Levofloxacin	LEV	5µg	≥17	14-16	≤13	30mm	Susceptible
2.Norfloxacin	NOR	10µg	≥17	13-16	≤12	14mm	Intermediately susceptible
3.Gentamicin	CN	10µg	≥15	13-14	≤12	10mm	Resistant
4.Chloramphenicol	C	30µg	≥18	13-17	≤12	11mm	Resistant
5.Trimethoprim	SXT	25µg	≥16	11-15	≤10	No zone	Resistant
6.Amoxicillin	AML	10µg	≥18	14-17	≤13	No zone	Resistant
7.Ciprofloxacin	CIP	5µg	≥21	16-20	≤15	12mm	Resistant

The effect of nanoparticles was tested against *Klebsiella pneumonia*. The nanoparticles in different concentrations (20, 40, 60, 80 and 100mg) were applied on *Klebsiella pneumonia* by submerging nanoparticles in whatman paper and

Levofloxacin was used as positive control. The results showed that nanoparticles have no effect on the growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* but Levofloxacin showed antibacterial potential.

Figure 6: The effect of nanoparticle on the growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia*

The results of the inhibition of *Bacillus subtilis* and *E. coli* growth demonstrated the antibacterial properties of the Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticle. Nanoparticles were employed in *Bacillus subtilis*, the largest zone of inhibition was seen at doses of 0.1, and there was no zone of inhibition at 0.025 or 0.05. The zone of

four distinct concentrations (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1) for antibacterial activity. Ciprofloxacin served as the activity's positive control. Zones of inhibition varied depending on concentration. inhibition was present in *E. coli* at doses of 0.025, 0.075, and 0.1, with a maximum at 0.05.

Table 5: The antibacterial effect of Cr doped manganese oxide on *Bacillus subtilis* and *E.coli*

Samples	Concentrations	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>E.coli</i>
Cr-55	0.025	0	7
	0.05	0	7.5
	0.075	5	7
	1	6	7

Positive control (Ciprofloxacin)	33	31
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Figure 7: Effect of Cr doped manganese oxide on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis*

Figure 8: Effect of Cr doped manganese oxide on the growth of *E.coli*

Figure 9: Graph represents the antibacterial property of NPs against the *Bacillus subtilis*

Figure 10: Graph represents the antibacterial property of NPs against the *E.coli*

Antifungal assay

To assess the antifungal potential of the nanoparticles the activity was performed on *Fusarium equesiti* and *Rhizopus stolonifer*. Results of antifungal activity were seen on the third, fifth, and seventh days. For the *Fusarium equesiti*, the maximum zone of inhibition was seen on day 7 and the minimum on day 3. The growth of *Rhizopus stolonifer* did not exhibit any impediment.

Zones of inhibition were 0.5, 0.6, 1.9, and 2 on the third day of *Fusarium equesiti* observation at doses of 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1, respectively.

The concentration of 0.1 produced the largest zone of inhibition and 0.025 the smallest. Zones of inhibition were 1.3, 1.8, 2.1, and 2.6 on the fifth day of *Fusarium equesiti* observation at doses of 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1, respectively. The concentration of 0.1 produced the largest zone of inhibition and 0.025 the smallest. Zones of inhibition for the *Fusarium equesiti* on the seventh day of observation were 2.2, 3, 4, and 4.5, respectively, for doses of 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1. The concentration of 0.1 produced the largest zone of inhibition and 0.025 the smallest.

Table 6: Table shows the concentrations and zones of inhibition at 3rd, 5th and 7th day for the fungus *Fusarium equesiti*

<i>Fusarium</i>	Concentration	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7
	0.025	0.5	1.3	2.2
	0.05	0.6	1.8	3
	0.075	1.9	2.1	4
	0.1	2	2.6	4.5

Figure 11: Control group of antifungal activity against *Fusarium equesiti*

Figure 12: Cr NPs at different concentration against *Fusarium equesiti* after 3rd day of incubation

Figure 13: Cr NPs at different concentration against *Fusarium equesiti* after 5th day of incubation

Figure 14: Cr NPs at different concentrations against *Fusarium equesiti* after 7th day of incubation

Figure 15: Graph represents the antifungal property of NPs against *Fusarium equesiti*

The development of *Rhizopus stolonifer* was not affected by the antifungal properties of Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticles. It began to expand on the third day and continued to grow the same on days five and seven.

Figure 16: Control group of antibacterial activity against *Rhizopus*

Figure 17: Cr NPs at different concentration against *Rhizopus stolonifer* after 3rd day of incubation

Figure 18: Cr NPs at different concentration against *Rhizopus stolonifer* after 5th day of incubation

Figure 19: Cr NPs at different concentration against *Rhizopus stolonifer* after 7th day of incubation
Antioxidant assay

The findings of the antioxidant activity test shows that ascorbic acid and Cr oxide NPs both exhibit antioxidant activity. Ascorbic acid has 83% antioxidant activity at the same concentration as Cr oxide NPs, which has maximal antioxidant

activity of 99%. The minimum antioxidant activity of the test sample is 89% at 0.1 concentrations. The outcomes demonstrated that when compared to ascorbic acid that Cr NPs has higher antioxidant activity.

Table 7: The table shows the concentrations of Cr doped manganese oxide and ascorbic acid used in this experiment and the percentage of antioxidant property of Cr doped manganese oxide and ascorbic acid at given concentrations.

Concentrations	Test Sample	Ascorbic acid
0.02	98%	81%
0.04	99%	83%
0.06	92%	85%
0.08	97%	86%
0.1	89%	90%
0.15	91%	87%
0.2	92%	85%

Figure 20: The graph shows the concentrations of Cr doped manganese oxide used in this experiment and the percentage of antioxidant property of Cr doped manganese oxide at given concentrations.

Discussion

The goal of the current study was to evaluate the ability of the Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticle to act as an antioxidant, antibacterial, and antifungal agent. To achieve that, Cr (NO₃)₂ was used to prepare Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticles. The

nanoparticle's characteristics were investigated. The PXRD results demonstrated monocrystalline nature, with a crystal size of 40.89, higher crystal stress, less defect severity, smaller crystalline size, stronger stability, increased crystal imperfection, and positive tensile micro strain values. The nanoparticle's amorphous nature,

heterodispersity, and rod-like structure were revealed by the SEM data. The specific surface area of the nanoparticle was calculated using the BET method, and its pore structure was examined using the DFT approach. Pore volume (V_m) (cc/g), surface area (SBET) (m^2/g), pore width (nm), and constant, respectively, were 38.86, 0.016, 3, 40, and 98.654 nm. The Mn-O bond vibration is validated by FTIR measurements that exhibit peaks below 750 cm^{-1} , while a straightforward FTIR pattern confirmed the strong Mn-O bond and high structural symmetry at 521.22 cm^{-1} . The PL results were acquired using a 375 nm excitation wavelength, and a sample spectrum was also recorded. The highest peaks were observed at 410 nm, while the lowest emission intensity was observed at 430 nm during excitation.

Rhizopus and Fusarium were treated with antifungal agents. For this, Fusarium and Rhizopus were removed from papaya and persimmon. In petri dishes, various NP concentrations (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1 mg/ml) and fungicide were applied. Days 3, 5, and 7 saw observations on the culture. On day 3, the concentration of 0.1 showed the highest zone of inhibition and 0.025 the lowest. Day 5 revealed a maximal inhibition zone at 0.1 concentrations and a minimum at 0.025. On day 7, the maximum zone of inhibition was at doses of 0.01 and the minimum was at 0.025. The outcomes demonstrated that the corresponding NPs have an antifungal impact on Fusarium. Bramhanwade et al. (2016) found concurrent outcomes when employing Cu nanoparticles to combat Fusarium. Fusarium c., F. oxysporum, and F. equiseti were chosen as the three different crop harmful fungi against which the in vitro antifungal efficacy of produced copper nanoparticles was investigated. It's interesting to note that the investigated crop pathogenic fungus was effectively combated by copper nanoparticles. These copper nanoparticles showed the greatest effectiveness against F. equiseti, i.e., the zone of inhibition was found to be 25 mm diameter, followed by F. oxysporum (20 mm), and F. culmorum (19 mm) The experiment was maintained in triplicate and the antifungal

activity was assessed using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method. According to current study results there was no effect of the NPs on the growth of Rhizopus.

It was tested on Klebsiella pneumonia, Bacillus subtilis, and E. coli for antibacterial activity. Five concentrations (20 mg, 40 mg, 60 mg, 80 mg, and 100 mg) of Cr-doped manganese oxide nanoparticles were tested for antibacterial activity using the disk diffusion method, and seven antibiotics (Levofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Trimethoprim, Amoxicillin, and Ciprofloxacin) were tested using the same technique. The antibiotic levofloxacin served as the standard. Nanoparticles have a negligible impact on the growth inhibition of Klebsiella pneumonia. Nanoparticles were utilized at four different doses (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1) to perform antibacterial activity on Bacillus subtilis and E. coli. In this activity, ciprofloxacin served as the positive control. Bacillus subtilis did not exhibit a zone of inhibition at doses of 0.025 or 0.05, and its zone of inhibition peaked at 0.1. The similar zone of inhibition was present in E. coli at doses of 0.025, 0.075, and 0.1, with a maximum at 0.05. The outcomes demonstrated that nanoparticles of manganese oxide doped with Cr have an antibacterial impact. Alam et al. (2022) used the trimetal oxide nanocomposite, which exhibited strong antibacterial activity against Escherichia coli. In order to evaluate the antibacterial properties of silver nanoparticles, Keshari et al. (2020) created them. Using the bacterial growth inhibition approach, the bacteriostatic and bactericidal activity of silver nanoparticles against Escherichia coli was assessed. Silver nanoparticles' antibacterial potency and Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) were calculated for the bacteria. The MIC value of silver nanoparticles was 8 mg/ml (E. coli) (Keshari et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

The current study was carried out to examine the biomedical applications (antioxidant, antifungal and antibacterial) of the Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticle. To assess the antibacterial activity the nanoparticles were applied upon

E.coli, Bacillus subtilis and Klebsiella pneumonia, the obtained results proved the antibacterial potential of nanoparticle. For antifungal activity the nanoparticles were applied against Rhizopus and Fusarium, the outcomes confirms the antifungal activity against Fusarium and no inhibition of Rhizopus growth by nanoparticle. The antioxidant activity proved the antioxidant activity of nanoparticles. The obtained results showed that Cr doped manganese oxide nanoparticle has maximum antioxidant, antifungal and antibacterial property. It is concluded that there should be more focus on the nanoparticles in biomedical field because it is cheap and has no side effects.

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